

1 Prdm14 controls expression of Xist.

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8 The Prdm family of nuclear factors has described functions. We hypothesized Prdm enzymes have site-specific modification activity relevant to transformation in humans. We demonstrate here control of the Xist non-coding RNA by Prdm14.

9 Citations

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